

Supplementary Information

(Notes + Figures)

Complete genome and QbD-guided reverse vaccinology

for *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01

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Supplementary Figure 1. QAST Circos view of multi-strain genome alignments for *Streptococcus iniae* isolates SIKU01–SIKU05. Circos plot generated by QAST, showing alignment of SIKU01–SIKU05 assemblies to reference genome (strain 89353), with tracks for reference coordinates, isolate alignments, ANY support, and read coverage.

Supplementary Figure 2. Genome alignment and synteny analysis between *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01 and *S. iniae* strain QMA0141 (9117) isolated from the Amazon River dolphin (*Inia geoffrensis*) in 1976. The top and bottom tracks represent the genomes of strains QMA0141 (9117) and SIKU01, respectively. Colored blocks indicate locally collinear blocks (LCBs) conserved between the two genomes, while grey shading links homologous regions. Multiple large-scale inversions and rearrangements are visible, suggesting genome structural divergence between strains. The conserved core genome is largely preserved, but structural plasticity and potential horizontal gene transfer events contribute to the observed variation. The scale bar indicates 0.5 Mb.

Supplementary Figure 3. Antigenic variation (gene carriage and sequence conservation) across 90 *S. iniae* genomes for 17 epitope-containing proteins identified from the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB). Amino acid identity was calculated for each candidate antigen using reciprocal DIAMOND BLASTP and multiple sequence alignment with MAFFT. The heatmap displays pairwise amino acid identity (%) of each antigen across 90 *S. iniae* genomes, with darker shades indicating higher conservation. Gene carriage analysis assesses performed to assess the presence or absence of each target protein, revealing varying levels of sequence conservation across isolates. Several targets, including GAPDH, enolase, and the 60 kDa chaperonin, showed > 98% conservation across nearly all genomes, while others such as LPXTG-anchored and metal substrate-binding proteins exhibited greater variability. Sortase A and trigger factor (TF) also show low conservation in some isolates, suggesting variable antigenicity within the population. **Entries labelled with SIKU01 locus tags correspond to predicted proteins in the SIKU01 reference genome.**

M0 biophysical landscape

Across the full *S. iniae* SIKU01 proteome (**M0**; N = 1,855), the distributions of Quality Attributes (CQAs) for CDS coding sequences (hydrophobicity (GRAVY), aliphatic index, instability index (II), isoelectric point (pI), molecular weight (MW), length (nt or/ aa), net charge (z) at pH 7, GC3 fraction, arginine content, and binding potential) and their correlations were well resolved (**Supplementary Fig. 4**). **Hydrophobicity** centered near neutrality (GRAVY mean -0.13 (SD 0.46) and median -0.22), displaying a biphasic pattern consistent with a mixed population of soluble and membrane proteins. **Isoelectric points** were similarly bimodal (pI mean 7.03 (SD 2.21) and median 6.51), reflecting acidic and basic proteome subpopulations (**Supplementary Fig. 4a**). **Protein length** spanned broadly (mean 321 aa, SD 207.0; median 281 aa), while **molecular weight** was similarly variable (MW mean 35.4 kDa, SD 20.5; median 31.4 kDa). **Instability index** was generally low-to-moderate (II mean 34.6 (SD 10.2); median 33.5). Composition-linked variables were narrow: **GC3 fraction** mean 0.28 (SD 0.05); median 0.28, **arginine content** mean 0.04 (SD 0.02); median 0.04. **Net charge at pH 7** clustered near zero (z mean -2.58 (SD 15.4); median -1.78), with the expected tight coupling to pI (**Supplementary Fig. 4a**).

Pairwise structure recapitulated known trends and revealed coherent clusters (**Supplementary Fig. 4b-g**). Hydrophobicity vs. aliphatic index showed a strong positive association ($\rho \approx 0.82$, $p < 10^{-15}$; **Supplementary Fig. 4d**), whereas hydrophobicity vs. binding potential was strongly negative (**Supplementary Fig. 4b**). Aliphatic index vs. binding potential was negatively sloped (**Supplementary Fig. 4e**), and arginine content increased with binding potential but decreased with hydrophobicity (**Supplementary Fig. 4f-g**). As expected, length and molecular weight (MW) were nearly collinear ($\rho \approx 1.00$), and pI vs. net charge (z) at pH 7 was tightly positive ($\rho \approx 0.93$). Amino-acid usage frequencies for the **M0** proteome are provided in

Supplementary Fig. 5, and a full Spearman correlation matrix summarizing these relationships is shown in Supplementary Fig. 6.

Supplementary Figure 4. Biophysical landscape of the proteome of *S. iniae* strain SIKU01

(M0). (a) Distributions of intrinsic features across all 1,855 predicted proteins, including aliphatic index, arginine content, binding potential, GC content at third codon positions (GC3), hydrophobicity (GRAVY), instability index (II), isoelectric point (pI), protein length (amino acids, aa), molecular weight (MW), and net charge (z) at pH 7. Mean, median, and standard deviation are shown in each facet. (b–g) Selected pairwise relationships highlighting strong or structured correlations: hydrophobicity vs. binding potential (b), pI vs. net charge at pH 7 (c), hydrophobicity vs. aliphatic index (d), binding potential vs. aliphatic index (e), binding potential vs. arginine content (f), and hydrophobicity vs. arginine content (g). Points are overlaid with density contours.

Supplementary Note 1 — Virulence-associated protein subset of *S. iniae* SIKU01

Based on InterPro domain architectures, Gene Ontology (GO) functional annotations, and gene name-based inference, a total of 283 proteins were identified as belonging to Critical Quality Attribute (CQA) categories relevant to *S. iniae* virulence (**Supplementary Table 14**). Functional annotation was derived from curated bioinformatics databases (InterPro, UniProt, and UniProtKB) and complemented by expert-driven literature validation using PubMed PMIDs, ensuring both computational and knowledge-based evidence. The functional risk space indicated that nutrient acquisition systems represented the most prevalent CQA group (> 100 proteins), followed by secretion systems (~ 25 proteins), immune evasion factors (~ 30 proteins), and adhesins (~ 25 proteins). Additional groups included toxins and hemolysins (e.g., TOMM-associated or pore-forming domains; ~ 6 proteins), capsular biosynthesis-related enzymes (~ 50 proteins), and infection-associated hydrolases such as nucleases, S8 family proteases, and other peptidases (~ 50 proteins).

Subcellular localization analyses of these 283 VFs further identified 31 proteins with N-terminal signal peptides (**Supplementary Table 5**), 164 proteins containing predicted transmembrane domains (**Supplementary Table 6**), and 112 predicted cytoplasmic antigen candidates (**Supplementary Table 7**).

Supplementary Figure 5. Summary of functional and physicochemical properties of virulence factors (VFs) identified in *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01. Top panels show distributions of VF types, protein lengths, molecular weights, and isoelectric points. Middle panels illustrate relationships between physicochemical parameters. Bottom panel shows amino acid composition of predicted VFs.

Supplementary Figure 6. Spearman correlation matrix of biophysical features in the *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01 proteome (M0). Pairwise ρ values, scatterplots, and density overlays illustrate relationships among intrinsic properties, including aliphatic index, binding potential, GC3 fraction, hydrophobicity, instability index (II), isoelectric point (pI), arginine content, molecular weight (MW), and net charge (z). Hydrophobicity and aliphatic index show a strong positive correlation ($\rho = 0.82$), while hydrophobicity is inversely correlated with binding potential ($\rho = -0.94$) and II ($\rho = -0.32$). Other associations, such as GC3 fraction with pI, are weaker but significant.

Supplementary Figure 7. Biophysical design space filtering of *S. iniae* proteins across early QbD stages. (a) M0: full proteome (N = 1,855 proteins) prior to any QbD filtering, projected by molecular weight (MW), hydrophobicity, and isoelectric point (pI). (b) Pre-M1: core genome subset showing proteins that pass M0 inclusion criteria (n = 1,374 proteins) after initial inclusion gates (valid CDS, full ORF, core carriage). (c) M1-general: survivors following application of physicochemical and evidence-based filters, reducing the design space to 1,101 candidates. Symbols are annotated by prior evidence (PubMed PMIDs, epitope, or both).

Supplementary Figure 8. Expression system and purification design spaces for downstream manufacturability filtering. (a) M1 Protein (*Escherichia coli*, (*E. coli*) candidates projected by MW, pI, and codon adaptation index (CAI), highlighting physicochemical compatibility with bacterial recombinant expression. (b) Plasmid DNA (pDNA) platform (*Danio rerio*, zebrafish) candidates filtered by nucleotide length, GC3 composition, and CAI. (c) pDNA platform (*Oreochromis niloticus*, Nile tilapia) candidates filtered by nucleotide length, GC3 composition, and CAI. Density contours indicate clustering of feasible antigens under each platform’s codon usage constraints. Final survivors represent platform-ready antigen pools compatible with host translation and manufacturing requirements.

Supplementary Figure 9. Quality by Design (QbD) lifecycle workflow for antigen selection and downstream purification strategy. (a) Target Product Profile (TPP) definition (antigen type, delivery route, expression system) and evaluation of Critical Material Attributes (CMAs). Antigens are scored in silico for Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) such as size, charge, conservation, codon adaptation, and predicted purification behavior. **(b)** Upstream funnel showing stepwise reduction from **M0** (protein-coding sequences, CDS; N = 1,855) → **Pre-M1** (core genome, n = 1,374) → **M1-general** survivors (n = 1,101). **(c)** From this shared pool, candidates branch into route-specific funnels: protein route (*E. coli* biofactory, n = 141) and plasmid DNA routes (zebrafish n = 212; tilapia n = 207). **(d)** **M2** downstream manufacturability options,

including silica and cellulose affinity fusions, ion-exchange chromatography, and plasmid DNA optimization.

Supplementary Figure 10. RPS (%) by host species (channel catfish, four-finger threadfin, golden pompano, hybrid striped bass, Japanese flounder, Nile tilapia, turbot). Violin plots summarize within-host distributions; horizontal bars mark means; jittered points represent individual experiments. Colors use a viridis-based palette keyed to host. Unless otherwise annotated in the data table, the pathogen is *Streptococcus iniae* (entries labeled *S. agalactiae* or *Edwardsiella tarda* reflect cross-protection tests reported by the original studies).

Supplementary Figure 11. Relative percent survival (RPS, %) by vaccine type across compiled *Streptococcus iniae* studies. Violin plots show the distribution (kernel density) per type; horizontal bars mark the mean. Jittered points represent individual experiments. Colors follow a viridis-based palette with legend names: DNA, DNA+Other, Inactivated, Live, Other, Protein. Higher RPS indicates greater experimental protection post-challenge.

Supplementary Figure 12. Head-to-head RPS (%) comparison of pDNA versus protein subunit vaccines. Violin plots depict the distribution per class with means indicated; jittered points represent individual experiments. Colors use a viridis-based palette. This view isolates the two most common platforms in the dataset to visualize their efficacy ranges and medians.